

Dendrochronological and wood-anatomical analysis of ship and cargo wood from the Colla Wreck, Co. Cork, Ireland

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This report outlines the results of dendrochronological and wood species analysis of the Colla Wreck and a selection of its cargo. The find was examined initially 14th September 2012 where a plan for analysis was drawn up. Sampling took place 24th January 2014 of non-oak components of both the ship construction itself and a selection of the cargo. It was endeavoured to select a representative sub-set of the wood types present although several examples of some types were deliberately chosen, to confirm their similarity through microscopic analysis. In this way 28 samples were taken, eight from the ship construction itself, 13 from ships chests or crates, five smaller timbers that might have been used as dunnage and two samples from the hoops from barrels.

The only objects that are found to be of ring-porous oak (*Quercus sp.*) are the remains of barrel staves (fig. 1) and heads (an example is shown in fig. 2) from the cargo. Twelve of these were sampled, two from heads and the remainder from barrel staves. Three different barrel sizes are represented in the ship's cargo, and parts from each of these size standards were sampled. Eleven of the 12 barrel samples could be dated.

Figure 1. Barrel staves from the cargo of the Colla Wreck.

The dating results

The dating position of the 11 dated samples from the barrels is illustrated in fig. 3. The period that the tree-ring curves from each sample covers is shown, with heartwood in light grey and sapwood in dark grey. Sapwood is preserved on three of the samples, and possible heartwood/sapwood boundary was preserved on one. The dendrochronological analysis allows the material analysed to be divided into several groups, separated in terms of the timber provenance (see below).

Two barrel head components belong to Group 1 and one of these has sapwood preserved. Allowing for missing sapwood (ca. 20 (-5+10) Hollstein 1980) the felling date for the trees used to make these two parts was felled in AD 1613-28 (green in the diagram).

Three barrel parts belong in group 2. Two of these have sapwood preserved, of which one has 20 sapwood rings, but not bark edge (fig. 4). Allowing for missing sapwood (15 (-8+6) Christensen & Havemann 1998) the felling date for the trees that were used for these three pieces is estimated to AD 1621 or shortly after (shaded in purple in the diagram).

Four parts are assigned to group 3. None of these have sapwood preserved. The outermost preserved complete tree-ring in the group is on find no. F167 (Z113006a), and it was formed in AD 1600. Allowing for the missing sapwood (c. 12 (-6+7) Wazny 1990) the felling date for the tree used for this barrel part can be estimated to be after AD 1610. This estimate can be taken as the dating for group 3, marked in blue in the diagram (fig. 3).

Figure 2. Component of a barrel head from the cargo of the Colla Wreck.

Finally, two more barrel pieces are dated, but are not assigned to any of the three groups. Find no. F45 (Z113001a) has only heartwood preserved and is from a tree that was felled after c. AD 1619. Find F111 (Z113010a) has possibly heartwood/sapwood boundary preserved, but this could not be confirmed. The tree used to make this part can have been felled c. AD 1619-34. This dating is marked in orange in the diagram.

Note that different sapwood estimates are used because the analysis shows that the barrels from the cargo are made of trees that have grown in different regions.

Figure 3. Dating diagram, Colla Wreck, barrel cargo

In spite of the wide variety of timber sources identified for the oak barrels parts, the estimated felling dates for these trees are very similar. Where no suitable dendrochronology samples have, as yet, been identified from the ship timbers we can use the accurate dating of the barrel cargo as a proxy, even if we allow that the barrels can have been re-used several times before the ship was wrecked. It is very likely that the ship was built in the first half of the 17th century.

Figure 4. Macro photo of the outermost sapwood on barrel stave F48. Bark edge is not preserved

Provenance

As mentioned above, the dendrochronological analysis suggest that the barrel material can be separated into three distinct groups. In table 1 the correlation between the tree-ring curves from each barrel part and each other is shown. Curves with good correlation are grouped together, as indicated. An average of the tree-ring curves for each group is made. The average for Group 1 is 213 years in length and covers the period AD 1396-1608 (Z113M001). The average for Group 2 is 115 years long, covering the period AD 1506-1620 (Z113M002). Finally, group 3 is 133 years in length and spans AD 1468-1600 (Z113M003).

As can be seen in table 2, the mean curves for the barrels are dating with quite a wide range of tree-ring data for Northern Europe. Group 1 is dating widely with site chronologies from Northern Continental Europe, and incidentally with tree-ring data from a ship, also shown to include timbers from Northern Continental Europe (Guibal pers comm).

Group 2 is dating chiefly with Scandinavian tree-ring data. It achieves significant correlation with data from a range of broadly contemporary Southern Scandinavian shipwrecks (Daly 2000a; 2009a), with data from Scotland shown also to be from timbers imported from South Scandinavia (Crone pers comm) and with a chronology for western Sweden (Bråthen 1982).

Group 3 is dating strongly with Southern Baltic material, for example with a chronology for Gdansk (Wazny pers comm) and with data from the timber cargo from another shipwreck, found in in the harbour at Cuxhaven (Daly 2014).

				Z113001a	Z113002a	Z113006a	Z113003a	Z113007a	Z113010a	Z113011a	Z113012a	Z113004a	Z113008a	Z113009a	
			Z113001a	*	-	-	-	1.37	-	1.46	2.39	-	-	2.33	
barrel	Z113M003	Group 3	Z113002a	-	*	3.94	2.45	1.92	-	2.6	2.86	2.88	1.16	-	
			Z113006a	-	3.94	*	4.15	2.8	-	2.2	1.54	-	-	-	
			Z113003a	-	2.45	4.15	*	3.2	-	2.95	1.65	2.46	-	-	
			Z113007a	1.37	1.92	2.8	3.2	*	-	2.38	2.28	1.27	-	\	
			Z113010a	-	2.6	-	-	-	*	4.54	4.55	-	-	-	
heads	Z113M001	Gr. 1	Z113011a	1.46	2.86	2.2	2.95	2.38	4.54	*	7.08	1.5	-	-	
			Z113012a	2.39	2.88	1.54	1.65	2.28	4.55	7.08	*	-	-	-	
Small barrel	Z113M002	Group 2	Z113004a	-	1.16	-	2.46	1.27	-	1.5	-	*	4.44	1.16	
			Z113008a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4.44	*	4.07
			Z113009a	2.33	-	-	-	\	-	-	-	-	1.16	4.07	*

Table 1. Colla wreck, Cork. Correlation between the tree-ring curves from the dated barrels with each other.

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Filenames	-	-	Z113M001	Z113M002	Z113M003	
-	start	dates	AD1396	AD1506	AD1468	
-	dates	end	AD1608	AD1620	AD1600	
JEvM001	AD1467	AD1675	8,47	-	4,78	Jeanne-Elisabeth ship (Guibal pers comm)
p8622M01	AD1490	AD1707	6,95	-	-	Pomorzyani Lanietta (Wazny pers comm)
GO12NZ01	AD1343	AD1617	6,72	-	4,49	Parchim, Germany (Göttingen University revised Daly 2007)
DM200004	30BC	AD1960	6,59	-	3,45	G Weser (Göttingen University)
G3120Z01	AD1388	AD1620	6,53	-	4,34	Bodenfelde, Germany (Göttingen University revised Daly 2007)
DM700001	AD631	AD1950	6,33	-	4,16	Southern Germany (Göttingen University)
GO10ZZ01	AD1470	AD1677	6,29	-	3,71	Güstrow, Germany (Göttingen University revised Daly 2007)
cuxbalksM1	AD1461	AD1622	6,18	-	6,34	Cuxhaven Wreck balk cargo (Daly 2014)
DM200003	AD1004	AD1970	6,04	-	-	Weserbergland (Göttingen University)
G341CZ02	AD1455	AD1667	5,89	-	4,02	Wennigsen, Germany (Göttingen University revised Daly 2007)
DM200006	AD914	AD1873	5,80	-	5,87	Lüneburger Heide (Göttingen University)
GO10HZ01	AD1428	AD1582	5,49	-	5,98	Güstrow, Germany (Göttingen University revised Daly 2007)
H128GM01	AD1363	AD1647	5,49	-	3,81	Bad Bramstedt (Hamburg University revised Daly 2007)
DM200005	AD915	AD1873	5,39	-	5,10	Niedersachsen; Nord (Göttingen University)
G3710Z01	AD1508	AD1694	5,18	-	6,38	Jork, Germany (Göttingen University revised Daly 2007)
PM670108	AD725	AD1985	5,41	-	8,30	Gdansk (Wazny pers comm)
PP144M02	AD1435	AD1596	5,54	-	8,58	PL Kartuzy-Klosterki (Wazny pers comm)
cuxstaves	AD1426	AD1622	5,19	-	13,29	Cuxhaven Wreck clapboard cargo (Daly 2014)
GO10EZ01	AD1451	AD1591	4,90	-	6,00	Güstrow, Germany (Göttingen University revised Daly 2007)
G3511Z01	AD1406	AD1575	4,85	-	6,19	Lüneburg, Germany (Göttingen University revised Daly 2007)
P719M001	AD1309	AD1551	4,53	-	6,88	Tolkwicko (Wazny pers comm)
0691006S	AD1375	AD1599	4,38	-	7,28	PL-Oliwa/Kathedrale (Wazny pers comm)
PP148M01	AD1453	AD1641	4,23	-	5,66	PL-Kwietniewo (Wazny pers comm)
PP140M01	AD1458	AD1647	4,04	-	6,38	PL Starzyno (Wazny pers comm)
H11KLM01	AD1385	AD1589	3,67	-	5,68	HL-Mengstr. 44 (Hamburg University revised Daly 2007)
0684001S	AD1463	AD1647	3,46	-	6,25	Starzyno (Wazny pers comm)
GO12PZ01	AD1408	AD1572	3,40	-	6,10	Rühn, Germany (Göttingen University revised Daly 2007)
midtjy17	AD536	AD1980	3,15	5,20	6,61	Mid Jutland (Christensen pers comm)
CD60IZ01	AD1450	AD1635	3,14	5,34	4,66	Ryomgård (National Museum of Denmark revised Daly 2007)
HO157M02	AD1359	AD1563	3,13	-	5,14	Rehna Deutsches Haus (Hamburg University revised Daly 2007)
Z043M001	AD1320	AD1577	3,09	-	5,70	FPL 77 4AM wreck (Daly 2009c)
H11ISM01	AD1389	AD1563	-	-	5,98	HL Alfstrasse 38 (Hamburg University revised Daly 2007)
B019M002	AD1374	AD1574	-	-	5,96	Helsingør Kulturværft two barrels (Daly 2009b)
PP126M02	AD1504	AD1615	-	-	5,90	Elblag (Wazny pers comm)
Z093M003	AD1425	AD1593	-	-	5,60	Vasa, two barrels (Daly 2013)
H125MM01	AD1490	AD1652	-	-	5,58	Oersdorf Dorfstr. (Hamburg University revised Daly 2007)
Z0309M01	AD1395	AD1561	3,81	5,30	3,59	Barcode ship BC09 (Daly 2010b)
8127M001	AD846	AD1771	-	5,56	4,47	Ålborg Østerå & Boulevarden (Daly 2000a, 2001)
SNorway ships	AD1304	AD1895	-	5,92	3,62	SNorway ships 63 timber mean (Daly unpubl.)
Z093M002	AD1454	AD1564	-	5,34	-	Vasa, four barrels (Daly 2013)
Z073m001	AD1385	AD1574	-	5,86	-	Barcode ship 14 (Daly 2011)
Z0307M01	AD1435	AD1585	-	5,89	-	Barcode ship BC07 (Daly 2010a)
Z089m001	AD1399	AD1581	-	6,46	-	Barcode ship 5 (Daly 2013)
00652M02	AD1405	AD1607	-	6,89	-	B&W Copenhagen Ship 2 (Daly 2000b)
Z040M001	AD1386	AD1567	-	7,84	-	Gåsehage Randers (Daly 2009a)
EP41592	AD1390	AD1592	-	8,27	-	Stirling Castle Episode 4 (Crone pers comm)
SM000012	AD1125	AD1720	-	9,92	-	West Sweden (Bräthen 1982)

Table 2. Colla wreck, Cork. Correlation values between the mean tree-ring curves from the barrels parts (groups 1, 2 and 3) and site and master chronologies from Northern Europe. The source of the curves is given.

The analysis

Measurement and analysis of the material is carried out using the program "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997) and for the calculation of the t-value the program "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) is utilised. For the analysis of the barrels, data from Northern Europe are used, kindly made available by dendrochronology laboratories in Queens University Belfast, Sheffield University, Göttingen University, Hamburg University, Art Academy Warsaw, National Museum of Denmark, Lund University.

Wood species

As mentioned above, a selection of the wood and timber from the ship and its cargo were examined to identify the wood species utilised. As it was quickly obvious that the timbers in the ship and cargo were not common temperate European species it was decided that a sub-selection would be analysed by Peter Gasson at the Botanic Gardens at Kew, England. Twenty-eight samples were taken for close examination and of these 10 were selected for identification at the Royal Botanic Gardens at Kew. In the tables below (tables 3 and 4) the result of these analyses are summarised, but Gasson's full report is included as an appendix to this (Gasson 2014).

The ship timbers

It was found that the framing timbers from the ship were, on superficial examination, all made from one timber type, and samples of two were taken for microscopic examination. The anatomy of these were identical, so just one (sample 33 find no 30) was sent for identification at Kew. Gasson concluded that this is an oak *Quercus sp.* but one of the radial porous species. If the ship is European then species of oak that the frames could be made from include the evergreen oak (*Quercus ilex*) or cork oak (*Quercus suber*). As Gasson points out however, there are a number of North American and Asian species with these anatomical features.

The ship's planking are all, on superficial examination, found to be of conifer wood. Six timbers were sampled for microscopic examination, including the wale and the keel. Three different conifers seem to be represented. The three planks and the keel have similar anatomy and are probably the same genus. Only the keel sample was therefore sent to Kew for identification. Gasson could not narrow down this sample to genus level, but suggests that it belongs to the Cupressaceae family.

The wale timber was also examined at Kew. Gasson found that this is of the *Pinus sp.* genus but cannot be more precise.

The ship construction included a number of roughly hewn timbers of unknown function. One of these was sampled (sample 37 find no 192) and found to be a conifer. A sub-sample of this was examined at Kew and confirmed to be from the pine genus (*Pinus sp.*), but it is a different species to the wale timber. If European we might have *Pinus pinaster* or maritime pine, but North American species cannot be ruled out.

The cargo timbers

A selection of the large ship crates, shorter boards and probable dunnage were selected for sampling for microscopic examination. It was attempted to select the range of wood types represented in the collection, by sorting through the material through superficial surface examination. Samples from several timbers that appeared similar were taken to confirm their similarity through microscopic examination.

At least six wood types are represented in the material, and six sub-samples were therefore sent to Kew for identification.

Ships chest

The larger ship's chest represented by two samples (Sample 22 (find no 62) and 23 find no 146)) and these both are probably of the same wood genus as a series of short boards (Samples 28, 29 & 30) and two probable dunnage pieces (Samples 48 & 49). A sub-sample of sample 22 was examined at Kew. Gasson found that this is from the Lauraceae family and there are several genera in this family that can provide timber.

Crates

Boards from smaller crates from the ship were also sampled. Two of these (samples 24 & 27) are of the same type while a third, sample 25, is another type, and might be the same as a gable piece for a chest (sample 32 below) but further examination would

have to be carried out to check this. A fourth is different again (Sample 26 find no 216 is of *Pinus sp.*). Sample 24 was examined at Kew and Gasson suggests that it is a mimosoid or caesalpinoid legume. Samples 34 and 38 are both from planks probably from the ship's crates or chests and are similar in anatomy. One of these, sample 38 was also examined at Kew and it is also found to be made from a mimosoid or caesalpinoid legume. If Gasson narrows his search down to South America the closest genus would be *Parkia* for this sample, but this genus also occurs outside the neotropics.

Gables

Two gable boards from the chests were also sampled for microscopic examination, chiefly because at least one (sample 32) appeared to be of a different wood type to the majority of the planking components. A sub-sample of this was sent to Kew. Gasson finds that the anatomy of this sample could be ebony (*Diospyros sp.*) but it could also belong to the *Sapotaceae* family. One of the boards from the crate (sample 25) might be a similar genus to this. The second gable sampled (sample 31) might be another mimosoid or caesalpinoid legume but additional examination would be needed to confirm this.

Dunnage and other wood

There are three pieces that were probably used as dunnage and two additional small pieces that could have had a similar function on board, all sampled for identification. Two of these, samples 48 & 49, have very similar characteristics as the ship's chest samples (samples 22, 23 etc) and can therefore be made from wood from the *Lauraceae* family. Sample 39 is a conifer, possibly *Picea sp.* Spruce. Sub-samples of two were examined at Kew. Sample 45 is a short faceted post made of a hardwood, but no identification was possible. Sample 40 however produced a better result. This unusual wood is identified as being of the genus *Gallesia sp.* Just two species of this genus listed in insidewood.lib.ncsu.edu (Wheeler 2011) and both these are native to South America.

Barrel parts

A sample of a hoop and withy from a barrel were sampled (the barrel staves and heads were of oak and were dated dendrochronologically (see above)). The hoop is made from a four-year-old rod of Chestnut (*Castanea sp.*) split in half along its length, which is a very typical way to make barrel hoops. The withy is from one-year-old willow (*Salix sp.*) shoot, also split in half along its length.

Other wooden artefacts from the ship including a pulley block and other ship equipment. These were not cut for identification. Through surface examination it could be seen that the pulley block components (11E363:188) and the sheave (11E363:324) were made from ring-porous wood, but given the exotic nature of this ship find, a detailed anatomical examination would be necessary to narrow down the genus of these and the other wood artefacts.

Discussion

The scientific dating for the Colla wreck is based on the dendrochronological dating of the oak barrels in the cargo. These are all made from trees that were felled around the 1620s, but as the provenance determination through dendrochronology shows, this material is from a mix of Northern European sources.

In Northern Europe, by the early 1600s, extensive trade in timber as a raw material took place including the trade in clapboards, which were very likely used as raw material for barrel making. In fact, a recently found wreck in Northern Germany (Segschneider pers comm; Auer pers comm), at the mouth of the River Elbe, contained a cargo of timber, including clapboards. These clapboards are dendrochronologically dated to winter AD 1622 (Daly 2014), fitting neatly within the same period as the Colla wreck. The clapboards are made from trees that grew in the Southern Baltic region, clearly demonstrating that the transport of such raw material took place in this period. In fact, the barrel parts from group 3 from the Colla wreck match very well with the tree-ring average from the Elbe wreck clapboards (table 2), underlining the possibility that the barrels in the Colla wreck could have been manufactured at a different location to where the trees came from.

The fact that several barrel sizes are found on the Colla ship from different forest sources is interesting to note, and allows us to think about the mechanism of procurement, transport and manufacture of these barrels, and how they ended up on this one ship. Barrels from different regions had different size standards, as has been shown previously (Daly 2005). Were there also different size standards of clapboard from different regions, or did the supply of Southern Baltic clapboards reach different destinations to those from Scandinavia?

With its cargo ranging from exotic coconuts, to Iberian ceramic, to Northern European barrels, the evidence from this ship find strongly indicates that it has contained a very wide range of cargo from many parts of the world. It was hoped that the timber identification would serve to give an indication of what parts of the world the exotic cargo might originate from, but this is not so readily possible, as much of the wood is difficult to identify to genus level.

To try to resolve this, we can use the archaeological evidence that is currently emerging to suggest the origin of these exotic cargo chests. Due to the presence of Northern European barrels on board, and other European goods (Iberian ceramics for example) we might work with the possibility that the ship itself was built around the Iberian Peninsula. The wood used would not go against this possibility. One of the chests was still intact and shut, when excavated (Julianna O'Donoghue pers comm). On opening, it was found to be empty. If the chest was still filled with a product when the ship sank, it had not survived the centuries under water. Maritime trade between the old and new worlds included Portuguese traders and one of the major products made in the New World and brought to the Old was sugar (Alexandre Monteiro pers comm). The large conical sugar blocks were transported in large timber chests. Sugar in a sealed chest would have dissolved, explaining the finding of an empty closed chest on the Colla wreck. Could the chests be from Brazil in South America, where major production of cane for sugar was feeding the European market? The chests that are known to have been used for transporting sugar from Brazil include tapinhoá (*Mezilaurus navalium*), jequitibá (*cariniana legalis* or *cariniana estrellensis*) and mogno (*swietenia tessmannii*) (Alexandre Monteiro pers comm). The first type, tapinhoá, is in the *Lauraceae* family, so if the chests originate in Brazil they could be this wood.

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Find no	Sample n	Description	object	position	species	Comments
30	33	ship	Framing timber		<i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak (cork oak/ evergreen oak?)	Kew
122	35	Ship	Wale	<i>Conifer</i> Same 26?	<i>Pinus sp.</i>	KEW
123	36	Ship	Plank		<i>Cupressaceae family</i>	Same as S41 (keel), S42, S4
192	37	Ship	Rough hewn unknown function		<i>Pinus sp.</i> (<i>pinaster?</i>)	Kew
64	41	Ship	Keel		<i>Cupressaceae family</i>	Kew
131	42	Ship	Plank		<i>Cupressaceae family</i>	Same as S41 (keel), S36, S4
1004	43	Ship	Plank		<i>Cupressaceae family</i>	Same as S41 (keel), S36, S4
32	44	Ship	Knee		<i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak cork oak/ evergreen oak	

Table 3. Colla Wreck, Cork. Table of the results of the wood analysis of selected wood from the ship.

Find no	Sample n	Description	object	position	Species	Comments
62	22	Cargo	Ship's chest side plank		<i>Lauraceae family</i>	Kew
146	23	Cargo	Ship's chest side plank fragment		<i>Lauraceae family</i>	Same as 22
47	24	Cargo	Ship's crate, board		mimosoid or caesalpinoid legume	Kew
106	25	Cargo	Ship's crate, board		unknown	Same as 32?
216	26	Cargo	Ship's crate, board	<i>Conifer</i>	<i>Pinus pinaster?</i>	Same as (35?) 37
79	27	Cargo	Ship's crate, board		mimosoid or caesalpinoid legume	Same as 24
133	28	Cargo	Short board		<i>Lauraceae family</i>	Same as 22
134	29	Cargo	Short board	Silver	<i>Lauraceae family</i>	Same as 22
84	30	Cargo	Short board	Reddish	<i>Lauraceae family</i>	Same as 22
191	31	Cargo	Ship's chest gable	Same as planks?	unknown	Same as 24?
39	32	Cargo	Ship's chest gable		<i>Diospyros sp.</i> (ebony) or <i>Sapotaceae</i>	Same as 31 KEW
147	34	Cargo	Plank (chest?)	Pale smooth wide ringed	mimosoid or caesalpinoid legume <i>Parkia?</i>	Same as 38??
58	38	Cargo	board	Pale	mimosoid or caesalpinoid legume. <i>Parkia?</i>	Same as S34 KEW
151	39	Cargo	Dunnage?	Conifer	<i>Picea?</i>	
259	40	Cargo	Thin board		<i>Gallesia sp.</i>	Kew Neotropics and temper Brazil or Temperate South America including Argentina, Chile, Uruguay, and S. Paraguay (insidewood.lib.ncsu.edu)
112	45	Cargo	Short facetted post	Same as chests?	Unknown	KEW
10	46	Barrel	Hoop		<i>Castanea sp.</i> , chestnut	4yr. old split in half
10	47	Barrel	withy		<i>Salix sp.</i> , willow	1 yr. old split half
102	48	Cargo	Dunnage?	? Same as 22	<i>Lauraceae family</i>	Same as S49
316	49	Cargo	Dunnage?	? Same as 22	<i>Lauraceae family</i>	

Table 4. Colla Wreck, Cork. Table of the results of the wood analysis of selected wood from the cargo.

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Filename	sample title and number	rings	start yr.	end yr.	Conversion	pith	sapwood	bark?	extra start	extra end	interpretation / felling
Z113001a	Culla Wreck Cork Ireland 11E363 F45 S62	207	AD1398	AD1604	T	G	0	N	N	N	after AD1619
Z113002a	Culla Wreck Cork Ireland 11E363 F116 S63	70	AD1524	AD1593	T	G	0	N	N	H1	after AD1603
Z113003a	Culla Wreck Cork Ireland 11E363 F7 S64	130	AD1468	AD1597	T	G	0	N	N	N	after AD1606
Z113004a	Culla Wreck Cork Ireland 11E363 F53 S65	100	AD1506	AD1605	R	G	2	N	N	S1	AD1610-24
Z113005a	Culla Wreck Cork Ireland 11E363 F140 S66	84			T	G	0	N	N	H1	undated
Z113006a	Culla Wreck Cork Ireland 11E363 F167 S67	119	AD1482	AD1600	T	G	0	N	N	H1	after AD1610
Z113007a	Culla Wreck Cork Ireland 11E363 F6 S68	111	AD1469	AD1579	T	G	0	N	N	N	after AD1588
Z113008a	Culla Wreck Cork Ireland 11E363 F51 S69	63	AD1527	AD1589	T	G	0	N	N	H1	after AD1597
Z113009a	Culla Wreck Cork Ireland 11E363 F48 S70	67	AD1554	AD1620	T	G	20	N	N	S1	AD1621
Z113010a	Culla Wreck Cork Ireland 11E363 F111 S71	85	AD1520	AD1604	T	G	0	?	N	N	AD1619-34?
Z113011a	Culla Wreck Cork Ireland 11E363 F155 S72	205	AD1396	AD1600	T	G	0	N	N	H1	after AD1616
Z113012a	Culla Wreck Cork Ireland 11E363 F155 S72	176	AD1433	AD1608	T	G	10	N	N	S1	AD1613-28
Z113M001	Culla Wreck Cork Ireland 11E363 barrel cargo 2 timber mean. Group 1	213	AD1396	AD1608							
Z113M002	Culla Wreck Cork Ireland 11E363 barrel cargo 3 timber mean. Group 2	115	AD1506	AD1620							
Z113M003	Culla Wreck Cork Ireland 11E363 barrel cargo 4 timber mean. Group 3	133	AD1468	AD1600							
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.											
Aoife Daly, Ph.D.						30 April 2014					

Table 5. Colla wreck, Schull, Co. Cork. List of objects analysed dendrochronologically.